

FREQUENCY OF INFECTION WITH POSTPARTUM INTRAUTERINE CONTRACEPTIVE

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Abstract

Objective: To determine the frequency of Infection with Postpartum Intrauterine Contraceptive.

Study Design: Cross-sectional study

Study Setting: Obstetrics and Gynecology Department, MNCH SSH, Faisalabad.

Study Duration: Six months (October'2023 to March'2024)

Methodology: A total of 369 healthy postpartum women aged 18–40 years who underwent PPIUCD insertion were enrolled using non-probability consecutive sampling. Exclusion criteria included preterm delivery, prolonged rupture of membranes, uterine anomalies, ectopic pregnancy, or postpartum hemorrhage. PPIUCD was inserted post-placentally or during cesarean section using a sterile no-touch technique. Follow-up was conducted at six weeks to assess clinical signs of infection, including foul-smelling discharge and fever $\geq 38^{\circ}\text{C}$.

Results: The mean age of participants was 28.53 ± 6.98 years; most (57.7%) were aged 18–30 years. Mean gestational age was 38.46 ± 1.15 weeks. Majority had secondary education (57.2%), belonged to the lower socioeconomic class (49.6%), and had parity of two (40.4%). Spontaneous vaginal delivery was observed in 58%, and 55% had BMI ≥ 25 . The overall frequency of infection was 8.1%. No statistically significant associations were observed between infection and age, gestational age, education, SES, parity, mode of delivery, or BMI. However, infection was significantly associated with foul-smelling discharge and fever ($p < 0.001$).

Conclusion: PPIUCD is a safe and effective method of contraception with a relatively low infection rate in the immediate postpartum period. Infection risk is more closely linked to symptomatic clinical indicators than to demographic or obstetric variables. Strengthening follow-up and counseling may enhance safety and acceptance of this method.

INTRODUCTION

Unintended pregnancies continue to pose a major global public health concern, exerting significant socioeconomic burdens on individuals and communities.¹ Short interpregnancy intervals are

associated with heightened risks of preterm birth, low birth weight, and preeclampsia. The World Health Organization recommends a minimum interval of 24 months² between pregnancies to reduce these risks.

Such spacing also facilitates complete uterine scar healing after cesarean deliveries, minimizes the risk of vertical transmission of infections, and aids maternal recovery from nutritional deficiencies sustained during pregnancy and lactation.³

The IUCD, a small plastic device placed within the uterus, is a widely used method of long-term reversible contraception.⁴ Previously, its insertion was commonly delayed until six weeks after childbirth, a timing associated with increased risks of unplanned pregnancies, diminished patient awareness about contraception, additional clinical visits, and a greater perception of side effects such as cramping and bleeding. However, immediate postpartum IUCD (PPIUCD) insertion offers a more convenient, cost-effective, and time-saving alternative with fewer logistical and clinical challenges.⁵

The immediate postpartum period is ideal for IUCD or implant placement due to the confirmed non-pregnant status of the mother and heightened motivation to avoid closely spaced pregnancies.⁶ PPIUCD insertion, done right after placental removal, is cost-effective and appropriate for women of all reproductive ages. It ensures early access to contraception and allows for immediate family planning counseling.⁷ Despite its effectiveness, IUCD use carries risks such as bleeding, uterine perforation, infections, and migration into nearby organs. In a study by Nalini et al., 80% of women received post-placental insertions, 18% post-cesarean, and 4% experienced infections.⁸

There is paucity of data on clinical benefits of Postpartum Intrauterine Contraceptive especially if we talk about Pakistan. The purpose of this study is to determine the outcome of Postpartum Intrauterine Contraceptive in terms of infection. If it is established that insertion during this period is associated with less discomfort then females will be motivated for contraception by this method..

METHODOLOGY:

This cross-sectional study was conducted at the Department of Obstetrics and Gynecology, Maternal Newborn and Child Healthcare, Faisalabad, over a period of six months (October'2023 to March'2024.) following approval of the synopsis from the College of Physicians and Surgeons Pakistan (CPSP) and Ethical Committee (Reference No: MNCH/Adm/23/868, Dated: 10-October-2023).

The objective was to determine the frequency of infection associated with postpartum intrauterine contraceptive device (IUCD) insertion.

A total of 369 participants were enrolled, based on a sample size calculated using the WHO sample size calculator with a 95% confidence level, an anticipated proportion of 4%, and an absolute precision of 2%. Patients were selected using a non-probability consecutive sampling technique. Inclusion criteria consisted of healthy females aged 18 to 40 years who underwent IUCD insertion. Women were excluded if they were between 48 hours and 6 weeks postpartum, had a history of prolonged rupture of membranes (more than 48 hours), experienced preterm labor (less than 37 weeks gestation), had known uterine abnormalities, or had a previous history of ectopic pregnancy or postpartum hemorrhage.

After obtaining approval from the institutional ethical review committee and CPSP, and securing informed consent from each participant, data collection commenced. Participants were briefed on the study's purpose and assured of confidentiality. Relevant demographic and clinical information, including age and parity, was recorded. For vaginal deliveries, IUCDs were inserted post-placentally, within 10 minutes of placental expulsion. Following active management of the third stage of labor, bimanual examination was performed to confirm uterine tone and emptiness. After antiseptic cleaning, a Sim's speculum was used to retract the posterior vaginal wall, and the anterior lip of the cervix was grasped using ring forceps. The IUCD was then inserted under sterile conditions using Kelly's forceps and no-touch technique. Women were asked to remain at rest for five minutes following insertion.

For intra-cesarean IUCD insertions, the device was introduced through the uterine incision and positioned at the fundus using the operator's index and middle fingers. Care was taken to direct the IUCD strings toward the cervix and to avoid their entrapment during uterine closure. Post-insertion counseling was provided, and participants were advised to return for follow-up at six weeks. At follow-up, participants were evaluated for signs of uterine infection, including foul-smelling vaginal discharge and fever $\geq 38^{\circ}\text{C}$. All observations and data were recorded using a specially designed proforma.

Data were analyzed using SPSS version 25.0. Quantitative variables such as age, gestational age, weight, height, and BMI were reported as mean \pm standard deviation. Categorical variables including education, socioeconomic status (SES), parity, type of delivery, symptoms, and infection were expressed as frequencies and percentages. The chi-square test was used to assess associations between categorical variables. Effect modifiers such as age, parity, BMI, gestational age, delivery type, education, SES, and symptoms were controlled through stratification. Post-stratification analysis was also conducted using the chi-square test, with a p-value \leq 0.05 considered statistically significant.

RESULTS:

The present study analyzed data from 369 postpartum women to assess various demographic and clinical characteristics. In Table 1 the mean age of the participants was 28.53 ± 6.98 years, with a majority (57.7%) aged between 18 and 30 years, and the remaining 42.3% falling in the 31 to 40 years age bracket. This indicates a relatively young reproductive population. The mean gestational age at the time of delivery was 38.46 ± 1.15 weeks. More than half of the women (52.3%) delivered between 37 and 38 weeks, while 47.7% reached a gestational age of 39 to 40 weeks, reflecting a predominance of term pregnancies. In terms of educational attainment, 57.2% of the participants had completed secondary education, followed by 23.8% with primary education, and 19.0% with tertiary education. This suggests that a significant portion of the sample had at least a basic level of schooling. Socioeconomic status (SES) distribution revealed that nearly half of the women (49.6%) belonged to the lower socioeconomic class, 34.4% were from the middle class, and 16.0% from the higher class, indicating a diverse but predominantly lower-income group.

Regarding parity, 40.4% of the participants had delivered twice previously, while 28.2% had one prior delivery. Furthermore, 17.1% had three deliveries, 3.8% had four or more, and 10.6% were primiparous, having had no previous births. This distribution suggests a moderate level of reproductive experience among the women. Delivery methods varied, with 58.0% undergoing spontaneous vaginal delivery (SVD) and 42.0% delivering by cesarean

section. This balance reflects common obstetric practice patterns. The mean body mass index (BMI) of the women was 25.62 ± 4.20 kg/m². When categorized, 45.0% of the women fell within the normal BMI range (18.5–24.9), while 55.0% had a BMI \geq 25, classifying them as overweight or obese. These findings highlight a notable prevalence of elevated BMI among postpartum women in the study population.

In the current study, Table 2 presents the frequency of infection following postpartum intrauterine contraceptive (PPIUCD) insertion was found to be 8.1%, with 30 out of 369 women experiencing clinical signs of infection within six weeks of insertion. The remaining 91.9% (339 women) did not develop any signs of infection. These findings suggest that the PPIUCD is generally a safe contraceptive option in the immediate postpartum period, with a relatively low infection rate.

In Table 3 Stratified analysis was performed to explore associations between postpartum IUCD infection and demographic as well as clinical characteristics. Among women aged 18–30 years, 16 (53.3%) experienced infection compared to 197 (58.1%) who did not, while in the 31–40 years group, 14 (46.7%) were infected and 142 (41.9%) remained infection-free, with no statistically significant difference ($p = 0.612$). Gestational age also showed no significant association ($p = 0.305$), as 13 (43.3%) infections occurred among those delivering at 37–38 weeks versus 17 (56.7%) at 39–40 weeks. In terms of education, infection was seen in 4 (13.3%) women with primary education, 17 (56.7%) with secondary, and 9 (30.0%) with tertiary education, again without statistical significance ($p = 0.165$). Socioeconomic status also had no meaningful effect ($p = 0.490$), with 18 (60.0%) infected women from the lower class, 8 (26.7%) from middle, and 4 (13.3%) from higher SES. Regarding parity, infection rates were distributed as 3 (10.0%) in parity 0, 10 (33.3%) in parity 1, 12 (40.0%) in parity 2, 4 (13.3%) in parity 3, and 1 (3.3%) in parity 4, with no significant association ($p = 0.963$). Mode of delivery ($p = 0.589$) and BMI category ($p = 0.338$) also did not show significant relationships; 16 (53.3%) infections occurred after SVD and 14 (46.7%) after C-section, while 16 (53.3%) were in women with BMI $<$ 25 and 14 (46.7%) with BMI \geq 25. However, both foul-smelling discharge and fever \geq 38°C were highly

significant predictors of infection ($p < 0.001$). Among women with foul-smelling discharge, 20 (66.7%) developed infection and none were infection-free, compared to 10 (33.3%) infections among those without discharge, all of whom were otherwise uninfected. Similarly, 11 (36.7%) of infected cases

had a fever, and none of the febrile women remained infection-free, whereas among afebrile women, 19 (63.3%) had infection and 339 (100%) did not, reinforcing the strong clinical link between these symptoms and IUCD-related infection.

TABLE 1: DEMOGRAPHICS AND CLINICAL INFORMATION

Variable	Category	Frequency	Percent
Age (Years)	18-30	213	57.7%
	31-40	156	42.3%
Gestational Age (Weeks)	37-38	193	52.3%
	39-40	176	47.7%
Education	Primary	88	23.8%
	Secondary	211	57.2%
	Tertiary	70	19.0%
Socioeconomic Status (SES)	Lower	183	49.6%
	Middle	127	34.4%
	Higher	59	16.0%
Parity	0	39	10.6%
	1	104	28.2%
	2	149	40.4%
	3	63	17.1%
	4	14	3.8%
Type of Delivery	SVD	214	58.0%
	C-Section	155	42.0%
BMI Category	Normal (18.5-24.9)	166	45.0%
	Obese (≥ 25)	203	55.0%

TABLE 2: FREQUENCY OF INFECTION WITH POSTPARTUM INTRAUTERINE CONTRACEPTIVE

Infection	Frequency	Percent
Yes	30	8.1%
No	339	91.9%

TABLE 3: STRATIFIED ANALYSIS OF INFECTION WITH POSTPARTUM IUCD

Variable	Group	Infection		Total	P-value
		Yes (Count & %)	No (Count & %)		
Age	18-30	16 (53.3%)	197 (58.1%)	213	0.612
	31-40	14 (46.7%)	142 (41.9%)	156	
Gestational Age	37-38	13 (43.3%)	180 (53.1%)	193	0.305
	39-40	17 (56.7%)	159 (46.9%)	176	
Education	Primary	4 (13.3%)	84 (24.8%)	88	0.165
	Secondary	17 (56.7%)	194 (57.2%)	211	
	Tertiary	9 (30.0%)	61 (18.0%)	70	
SES	Lower	18 (60.0%)	165 (48.7%)	183	0.490
	Middle	8 (26.7%)	119 (35.1%)	127	
	Higher	4 (13.3%)	55 (16.2%)	59	
Parity	0	3 (10.0%)	36 (10.6%)	39	0.963
	1	10 (33.3%)	94 (27.7%)	104	
	2	12 (40.0%)	137 (40.4%)	149	
	3	4 (13.3%)	59 (17.4%)	63	
	4	1 (3.3%)	13 (3.8%)	14	
Type of Delivery	SVD	16 (53.3%)	198 (58.4%)	214	0.589
	C-Section	14 (46.7%)	141 (41.6%)	155	
BMI	<25	16 (53.3%)	150 (44.2%)	166	0.338
	>25	14 (46.7%)	189 (55.8%)	203	
	Yes	20 (66.7%)	0 (0.0%)	20	0.000

Foul Smelling Discharge	No	10 (33.3%)	339 (100.0%)	349	0.000
Fever $\geq 38^{\circ}\text{C}$	Yes	11 (36.7%)	0 (0.0%)	11	
	No	19 (63.3%)	339 (100.0%)	358	

DISCUSSION

This study evaluated the frequency of infection following postpartum intrauterine contraceptive device (PPIUCD) insertion among 369 women and assessed associations with various demographic and clinical factors. The findings provide important insights into the safety and acceptability of PPIUCD in a real-world setting in Pakistan.

In terms of demographic characteristics, the mean age in our study was 28.53 ± 6.98 years, with 57.7% of women aged 18–30 years and 42.3% aged 31–40 years. This is consistent with the population studied by Khalid et al (2023),⁹ where the mean age in the PPIUCD group was 26.50 ± 5.05 years and 28.25 ± 4.40 years in the interval IUCD group. Similarly, in the trial by Averbach et al. (2023),¹⁰ the mean age was 29.9 ± 5.4 years, reflecting a comparable young reproductive cohort. These findings reinforce that PPIUCD is commonly accepted by women in their 20s and early 30s, which is a critical age for birth spacing and fertility control. The mean gestational age in our study was 38.46 ± 1.15 weeks, and the majority delivered at term (52.3% at 37–38 weeks, 47.7% at 39–40 weeks). These figures align closely with those in Khalid et al (2023),⁹ where gestational ages were 38.94 ± 1.42 weeks (PPIUCD group) and 39.08 ± 1.29 weeks (interval group).

With regard to educational status, our study population had a majority of women with secondary education (57.2%), followed by primary (23.8%) and tertiary education (19.0%). These findings are in partial agreement with Sisay et al. (2023),¹² who found that higher education levels were significantly associated with better knowledge and positive attitudes toward PPIUCD in Ethiopia. Similarly, Terefe et al¹³ (2023) also concluded that women with secondary or higher education were more likely to intend to use PPIUCD. In terms of socioeconomic status, 49.6% of our participants belonged to the lower class, 34.4% to the middle, and 16.0% to the higher class. This distribution reflects the demographic served by public sector facilities in Pakistan. In contrast, studies like that by Bolling et al

(2023),¹⁵ which included data from both high- and low-income countries, showed a much broader SES spread and highlighted the limited uptake of PPIUCD in high-income settings.

The parity profile in our study showed that 40.4% of women had two previous deliveries, while 28.2% had one, and 17.1% had three prior births. Only 10.6% were primiparous. These findings are in line with those of Aamir et al. (2018),¹⁶ who also observed that multiparous women were more likely to accept PPIUCD, and that acceptance rates were higher among women familiar with childbirth and spacing needs. As for delivery mode, 58.0% of our cohort underwent spontaneous vaginal delivery and 42.0% cesarean section. This aligns with the study by Qazi et al. (2020),¹⁴ which compared intra-cesarean and post-vaginal IUCD insertions and found vaginal insertions to be more common (84.4%). However, their findings also noted differing complication rates between the two methods, especially in terms of string visibility and expulsion.

The mean BMI in our study was 25.62 ± 4.20 kg/m², with 55.0% categorized as overweight or obese. While BMI was not reported in most reference studies, the elevated rates of overweight and obesity in our sample underscore the importance of offering safe contraceptive options like IUCDs that are not weight-dependent. Regarding infection rates, we observed an infection frequency of 8.1%. This figure is higher than the 4% infection rate reported by Nalini et al. (2023) in their tertiary care study. Khalid et al. (2023)⁹ also found a lower infection rate—2 cases in the PPIUCD group compared to 6 in the interval IUCD group—with no statistically significant difference ($p = 0.147$). Similarly, Averbach et al. (2023)¹⁰ found very low infection rates in both early and interval placement groups in a U.S.-based clinical trial. Safdar et al. (2022),¹¹ in their large-scale study from Lahore General Hospital, noted a 4.7% rate of vaginal infections among PPIUCD users, which is still below the infection rate observed in our study.

Interestingly, stratified analysis in our study revealed no statistically significant association

between infection and age, gestational age, education, SES, parity, type of delivery, or BMI. However, foul-smelling vaginal discharge and fever $\geq 38^{\circ}\text{C}$ were both significantly associated with infection ($p < 0.001$). This strong association aligns with clinical diagnostic criteria and reinforces the reliability of our infection definition. Several studies including Shaikh N and workers¹⁸ also reported on IUCD-related complications, such as expulsion and discomfort. For example, Aamir et al. (2018)¹⁶ reported a 3.9% expulsion rate and highlighted infections, menstrual irregularities, and cramping as common reasons for discontinuation. Safdar et al. (2022)¹¹ found expulsion in 24%, cramping in 25%, and vaginal discharge in 16% of patients, although their study relied heavily on telephonic follow-ups. In contrast, our study had a relatively low expulsion-related issue as the focus was on infection only, and clinical follow-up was conducted at six weeks.

Lastly, Bolling et al. (2023),¹⁵ in their systematic review, concluded that PPIUCDs are generally safe and effective, with complications like expulsion and infection being rare but variable, depending on insertion timing and population characteristics. This reinforces our study's overall conclusion that PPIUCD remains a safe and acceptable contraceptive method, especially in low-resource settings where continuity of care may be difficult postnatally.

CONCLUSION

This study demonstrates that the postpartum intrauterine contraceptive device (PPIUCD) is a generally safe and well-tolerated method of contraception, with an overall infection rate of 8.1%. While no significant associations were observed between infection and demographic or obstetric variables such as age, parity, gestational age, mode of delivery, BMI, socioeconomic status, or education level, the presence of foul-smelling vaginal discharge and fever $\geq 38^{\circ}\text{C}$ were strongly linked to infection. These clinical symptoms serve as reliable indicators for early detection of IUCD-related infection. The findings support the routine offering of PPIUCD during the immediate postpartum period, especially in low-resource settings where postpartum follow-up may be limited. Enhancing post-insertion counseling and symptom monitoring can further improve patient outcomes and method continuation. Further

multicenter and longer-term studies are recommended to validate these findings and address long-term complications such as expulsion and discontinuation.

REFERENCE:

1. Iftikhar P M, Shaheen N, Arora E. Efficacy and Satisfaction Rate in Postpartum Intrauterine Contraceptive Device Insertion: A Prospective Study. *Cureus*. 2019; 11(9): e5646.
2. Tounkara MS, Ingabire R, Comeau DL, Karita E, Allen S, Nyombayire J, et al. A mixed-methods study of factors influencing postpartum intrauterine device uptake after family planning counseling among women in Kigali, Rwanda. *PLoS ONE*. 2022; 17(11): e0276193.
3. Gebremedhin M, Alemayehu A, Yihune M, Dessu S, Melis T, Nurahmed N. Acceptability and Factors Associated with Immediate Postpartum Intrauterine Contraceptive Device Use Among Women Who Gave Birth at Government Hospitals of Gamo Zone, Southern Ethiopia, 2019. *Open Access J Contracep*. 2021;12 93–101.
4. Sisay FA, Ayalew AB, Erega BB, Ferede WY. Factors associated with knowledge of the postpartum intrauterine contraceptive device and attitude towards its use among women attending antenatal care at Debre Tabor town, Northwest Ethiopia, 2021: a cross-sectional study. *Contracep Repro Med*. 2023; 8:1-14.
5. Escobar M and Shearin S. Immediate postpartum contraception: intrauterine device insertion. *J Midwifery Womens Health* 2019; 64(4): 481–487.
6. Khanzada B, Shahani MJ, Khanzada AK. Immediate postplacental insertion of intrauterine contraceptive device (copper 375) and its complications in term of expulsion, infection and perforation. *Clin J Obstet Gynecol*. 2018; 1: 082-086.
7. Shaikh F, Shaikh S, Basma, Sonia, Akhtar T. Postpartum Intrauterine Contraceptive Device During Cesarean Section: Safe and

- Effective Procedure. *J Surg Pak.* 2019; 24 (2):71-75.
8. Nalini N, Singh B, Jha S, Singh AV. Acceptance, safety and efficacy of postpartum intrauterine contraceptive device. *J Family Med Prim Care* 2023; 12:868-73.
9. Khalid H, Syed SZ, Waheed F, Iqbal F, Mehmud Q, Khalid A. Comparison of Complication of Postpartum Intrauterine Contraceptive Device With Interval Placed IUCD: PPIUCD VS Interval Placed IUCD. *Pak J Health Sci.* 2023;4(10):36-40. <https://doi.org/10.54393/pjhs.v4i10.1018>
10. Averbach S, Kully G, Hinz E, Dey A, Berkley H, Hildebrand M, et al. Early vs interval postpartum intrauterine device placement: a randomized clinical trial. *JAMA.* 2023 Mar 21;329(11):910-7. <https://doi.org/10.1001/jama.2023.1405>
11. Safdar Z, Sabir SF, Zaib S, Abid S. Female's Experience with Post-placental Intrauterine Contraceptive Device Use in a Tertiary Care Centre in Pakistan. *Reprod Health.* 2022 May;88.
12. Sisay FA, Ayalew AB, Erega BB, et al. Factors associated with knowledge of the postpartum intrauterine contraceptive device and attitude towards its use among women attending antenatal care at Debre Tabor town, Northwest Ethiopia, 2021: a cross-sectional study. *Contracept Reprod Med.* 2023;8:7. <https://doi.org/10.1186/s40834-022-00202-y>
13. Terefe G, Wakjira D, Abebe F. Immediate postpartum intrauterine contraceptive device use among pregnant women attending antenatal clinics in Jimma town public healthcare facilities, Ethiopia: Intentions and barriers. *SAGE Open Med.* 2023 Mar;11:20503121231157212. <https://doi.org/10.1177/20503121231157212>
14. Qazi Q, Liaqat N, Hussain SS, Khattak S. The effectiveness of insertion of immediate postpartum intrauterine contraceptive device (IPP-IUCD) in terms of modes of delivery. *J Med Sci.* 2020 Dec 31;28(4):367-71.
15. Bolling KR, Wahdan Y, Warnock N, Lott J, Schoendorf J, Pisa F, et al. Utilisation, effectiveness, and safety of immediate postpartum intrauterine device insertion: a systematic literature review. *BMJ Sex Reprod Health.* 2023 Apr 1;49(2):e1.
16. Aamir F, Mahesh A, Karim SA. To Evaluate the Compliance of Postpartum Intrauterine Contraceptive Device at Jinnah Medical College Hospital. *Ann Abbasi Shaheed Hosp Karachi Med Dent Coll.* 2018 Jun 30;23(2):79-85.
17. Nalini R, Singaravelu S, Shankar R. Acceptance, effectiveness and complications of postpartum intrauterine contraceptive device (PPIUCD): a prospective study in a tertiary care centre. *J Family Med Prim Care.* 2023;12(1):180-4. https://doi.org/10.4103/jfmprc.jfmprc_1166_22
18. Shaikh N, Rehman F, Hussain M. Safety and effectiveness of postpartum intrauterine contraceptive device (PPIUCD) during cesarean section. *J Pak Med Assoc.* 2019;69(1):39-43.